

Chlorpromazine Hydrochloride as a New Redox Indicator in Cerimetry

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The optimum conditions for the successful use of chlorpromazine hydrochloride as redox indicator in the cerimetric titration of iron(II), molybdenum(V), hydroquinone and ascorbic acid in sulphuric, hydrochloric and acetic acid media have been developed. The indicator gives sharp reversible colour change at the equivalence point. Its formal redox and transitional potentials have been determined. Its sensitivity towards various oxidising agents are reported. It has certain advantages over the existing redox indicators in cerimetry.

CHLORPROMAZINE hydrochloride, CPH, 2-chloro-10 (3-dimethylamino-n-propyl) phenothiazine hydrochloride was used as redox indicator in vanadimetry¹. CPH was stated to be useless as redox indicator in cerimetry². In the present communication the authors have made detailed investigations of the indicator properties of CPH and proposed it as a sensitive indicator in the titration of iron(II), molybdenum(V), hydroquinone and ascorbic acid with cerium(IV) sulphate.

Experimental

Reagents:

A 0.1% solution of CPH was prepared in doubly distilled water and stored in an amber bottle.

Approximately 0.05*N* and 0.01*N* solutions of molybdenum(V)³ and hydroquinone⁴ were prepared and standardised against cerium(IV) sulphate solution.

Approximately 0.1*N* ascorbic acid solution was prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity of analar ascorbic acid (S. Merck) in one litre of metal free doubly distilled water containing 0.5 g of analar EDTA and 4 g of analar formic acid. The solution was standardised against potassium iodate⁵.

Apparatus:

The potentiometric assembly consisted of a direct reading potentiometer, a mirror galvanometer, a bright platinum gauze indicator electrode, a saturated calomel reference electrode and an agar salt bridge. The titration mixture was stirred by a magnetic stirrer.

General Procedures :

Determination of the formal and transition potentials of CPH:

The formal redox potential of CPH was determined by the method of Schilt⁶. The transition potentials of CPH in the titration of iron(II) with cerium(IV) sulphate in acetic acid medium were determined by the potentiometric method¹.

Determination of sensitivity of CPH towards various oxidizing agents:

The sensitivity of CPH towards various oxidizing agents was determined by mixing a drop of vanadate, bromate, iodate, dichromate, cerium(IV) sulphate or ferricyanide, a drop of 2*N* hydrochloric acid and a drop of 1% CPH solution in a spot plate. Each test was allowed to stand for 30 sec. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SENSITIVITY OF CPH TOWARDS SIX OXIDISING AGENTS

Oxidant	V ⁵⁺	BrO ₃ ⁻	Cr ₂ O ₇ ²⁻	Ce ⁴⁺	IO ₃ ⁻	[Fe(CN) ₆] ³⁻
Identification limit (μg)	0.0456	0.056	0.064	0.134	0.385	1.133
Dilution limit	1:5.855x10 ⁵	1:4.764x10 ⁵	1:1.709x10 ⁵	1:1.99x10 ⁵	1:6.928x10 ⁴	1:23.61x10 ⁵

Cerimetric titration of iron(II), molybdenum(V), hydroquinone and ascorbic acid:

20 ml of 0.05-0.01*N* iron(II), molybdenum(V) or hydroquinone, 1 ml of 0.1% CPH indicator and phosphoric acid were diluted to 40 ml with sulphuric, hydrochloric or acetic acid and titrated with 0.05-0.01*N* cerium(IV) sulphate solution to the appearance of pink or orange-red colour.

20 ml of 0.1-0.05*N* ascorbic acid and 1 ml of 0.1% CPH were diluted to 40 ml with sulphuric, acetic, hydrochloric or phosphoric acid and titrated with cerium(IV) sulphate. CPH is added near the end-point in hydrochloric acid medium. The titration conditions, colour changes at the end-points and results are given in Table 2.

indicator must have suitable redox and transition potentials which should lie within the potential break in the potentiometric titration curve. The selected indicator should have a colour change at the potential as close possible to the equivalence point. Of the three methods used for determining the redox potential of a redox indicator, the methods of Bishop and Crawford¹¹ and Smith and Banick¹² failed to give the accurate value for the redox potential of CPH. The method of Schilt⁶ was used to find the redox potential of CPH in varying concentration of sulphuric acid at 20°. A plot of potential versus time in different concentrations of sulphuric acid showed that the formal potential decreases very slowly with increasing time and acid concentration. The potentials extrapolated to zero time in 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1.00, 1.25 and 1.5*M* sulphuric acid

TABLE 2—CERIMETRIC DETERMINATION WITH CPH INDICATOR

Sl. No.	Reductant taken (mg)	Medium	Normality of Cerium(IV) sulphate	Reductant determined (mg)	Colour change at the end-point
1)	Iron(II)	3-6 ml of 10 <i>M</i> H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.50 - 1.0 <i>M</i> H ₂ SO ₄ or HCl/0.5-2.5 <i>M</i> HAC	0.1	Iron(II)	Almost colourless to pink —do—
	113.71			113.71	
	55.73			55.73	
2)	Molybdenum(V)	1-4 ml of 10 <i>M</i> H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.2-0.5 <i>M</i> H ₂ SO ₄ /1.0-2.0 <i>M</i> HCl/0.5-3.0 <i>M</i> HAC	0.05 0.01	Molybdenum(V)	Colourless to pink
	193.8			193.8	
	94.76			94.76	
3)	Hydroquinone	2-4 ml of 10 <i>M</i> H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.5-1.0 <i>M</i> H ₂ SO ₄ /0.5-0.7 <i>M</i> HCl/0.6-3.0 <i>M</i> HAC	0.1 0.05 0.01	Hydroquinone	Light yellow to orange red
	111.5			111.5	
	55.38			55.38	
4)	Ascorbic acid	2-6 ml of 10 <i>M</i> H ₃ PO ₄ + 1-2 <i>M</i> HAC/0.5-1.0 <i>M</i> H ₂ SO ₄ —do— 2-3 ml of 10 <i>M</i> H ₃ PO ₄ + 1-2 <i>M</i> HCl —do— 1-2 <i>M</i> H ₃ PO ₄ —do— —do— —do— —do— —do— —do— —do— —do— —do— —do—	0.1 0.05 0.1 0.05 0.1 0.05 0.01 0.005 0.005 0.002 0.002	Ascorbic acid	Colourless to pink —do— Colourless to pink —do— —do— —do— —do— —do— —do— —do— —do— —do— —do— —do— —do—
	166.2			166.2	
	88.49			88.51	
	166.2			166.2	
	88.38			88.40	
	166.8			166.8	
	83.59			83.60	
	17.60			17.62	
	8.49			8.51	
	4.12			4.13	
	2.18			2.19	
	0.8			0.82	
	0.4			0.42	

Results and Discussion

CPH is highly soluble in water giving colourless solution which is stable for about a week at room temperature (27°) and for three months at low temperature (8°). It undergoes reversible one electron oxidation to a red intermediate^{7,8} which is believed to be a radical cation^{9,10}. The radical cation is irreversibly oxidized to a colourless sulphoxide⁸ with the loss of one more electron.

Determination of the formal redox and transition potentials:

It is necessary when choosing a redox indicator for a particular redox titration to ensure that its formal redox potential lies within those of redox systems. The

were found to be 799, 788, 760, 753, 732 and 721 mV respectively. The values were accurate to ± 5 mV.

It is not possible to get accurate values for the transition potentials of CPH in the titration of iron(II) with cerium(IV) sulphate in sulphuric or hydrochloric acid medium as the potential at which CPH gives the first trace of end-point pink colour is not stabilised. However the steady transition potentials are obtained in acetic acid medium 90 seconds after the addition of the last drop of cerium(IV) sulphate which marks the end-point. The transition potentials of CPH in the titration of iron(II) with cerium(IV) sulphate in 0.50, 1.00, 1.50, 2.0 and 2.5*M* acetic acid solution containing 0.25*M* phosphoric acid and 0.25*M* sulphuric acid, were found to be 760, 756, 752, 748 and 745 ± 5 mV respectively at 28°. The values of the redox and transition

potentials of CPH indicate that CPH serves as a good indicator in the titration of iron(II), molybdenum(V), hydroquinone and ascorbic acid with cerium(IV) sulphate.

The results in Table 1 shows that the sensitivity of CPH towards six oxidising agents is $V^{5+} > BrO_3^- > Cr_2O_7^{2-} > Ce^{4+} > IO_3^- > [Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}$.

Titration of 0.1-0.01N iron(II) ammonium sulphate

CPH does not give sharp end-points in the titration of iron(II) with cerium(IV) sulphate in hydrochloric, sulphuric or acetic acid medium because of the slow reduction of the red radical cation by iron(II). It gives sharp and correct end-points in 0.5-1.0M sulphuric or hydrochloric or 0.5-2.5M acetic acid solution containing 3-6 ml of 10M phosphoric acid in a total volume of 60 ml. Sluggish end-points are obtained at acidities higher than 1.0M sulphuric or hydrochloric acid even in the presence of phosphoric acid. Premature end-points and precipitation are obtained in acetic acid medium stronger than 2.5M. Phosphoric acid (10M) less than 3 ml gives sluggish end-points and more than 6 ml gives premature end-points. The colour change at the end-point is from almost colourless to pink. The end-point colour is stable for more than 10 hours.

It was found that 0.8-2.0ml of 0.1% CPH solution is necessary in a total volume of 60 ml for proper indicator action. Higher concentration of the indicator gives higher titre values.

The indicator correction needed for CPH has been found by comparing the results from the potentiometric titrations with those when CPH was used. The average indicator correction is 0.02 ml of 0.01N cerium(IV) sulphate for 1 ml of 0.1% CPH solution.

Experiments have shown that stannic chloride, mercuric chloride and mercurous chloride do not interfere with the function of CPH indicator in the titration of iron(II) with cerium (IV) sulphate. CPH can therefore be usefully employed in the determination of iron(III) present in ferric alum or in haematite after the conventional method of reduction of iron(III) by stannous chloride.

CPH is superior to ferroin indicator in that it is more sensitive requiring less indicator correction and it works in the presence of acetic acid.

Titration of 0.1-0.01N molybdenum(V)

Ferroin^{3,13,14}, diphenylbenzidine¹⁵ (DB) and many other indicators were proposed in the titration of molybdenum(V) with cerium(IV) sulphate. Ferroin which is most commonly used in cerimetry functions only in 3M hydrochloric acid in the presence of syrupy phosphoric acid¹⁵. Grubitsch et al¹⁶ proposed 4M hydrochloric acid for using ferroin indicator. DB works in 4M hydrochloric acid.

CPH gives sharp colour change from colourless to pink at the equivalence point in acid media ranging from 1-2.0M hydrochloric, 0.2-0.5M sulphuric or 0.5-3.0M acetic acid solution containing 1-4 ml of 10M phosphoric acid in a total volume of 60 ml. The indicator gives unstable end-points at higher acidities. 0.8-2.0 ml of 0.1% CPH is required for proper indicator action in a total volume of 60 ml. With lower and higher concentration of CPH indicator, the end-points are sluggish and are not easily reversible. The end-point colour is stable for 15-150 min. in 0.5-0.2M sulphuric acid, 60-120 min. in 2.0-1.0M hydrochloric acid and 20-25 min. in acetic acid medium.

CPH is superior to ferroin in that i) it works at lower acidities, ii) it is more sensitive requiring less indicator correction and iii) it functions satisfactorily in acetic acid medium.

Titration of 0.1-0.01N hydroquinone

Diphenylamine¹⁷, methyl red¹⁷, ferroin¹⁸, Rhodamine 6G (Rh)¹⁹, NPA¹⁹, crystal violet¹⁹ (CV), alphazurin G²⁰, *p*-ethoxy chryslodine²¹, setopalin²², eriogreen²², erioglaucine²² and promethazine hydrochloride²³ were proposed as indicators in this titration. Most of these indicators are unsatisfactory for one reason or another. Diphenylamine requires a large indicator correction to bring the values in agreement with potentiometric values. Methyl red is added near the end-point and the colour change is not satisfactory. Rh, NPA and CV work in the titration with only 0.05N cerium (IV) sulphate. Setopalin, eriogreen, erioglaucine are added in the beginning and near the end-point of the titration and the end-point colour is stable only for a few seconds. Ferroin needs an indicator correction of 0.1 ml of 0.01N cerium(IV) sulphate.

CPH gives sharp and correct end-points in 0.5-1.0M sulphuric, 0.5-0.7M hydrochloric or 0.6-3.0M acetic acid solution containing 2-4ml of 10M phosphoric acid in a total volume of 60 ml. It gives a reversible colour change from light yellow to orange red at the equivalence point. The end-point colour is stable for 10-5 min. in 0.5-1.0M sulphuric, 10 min in 0.5-0.7M hydrochloric and 30-20 min in acetic acid media. It gives sluggish and premature end-points at higher acidities of sulphuric, hydrochloric and phosphoric acid because of the slow reduction of the oxidized indicator by hydroquinone. Higher concentration of acetic acid leads to precipitation. 0.8-2.0 ml of 0.1% CPH is required for proper indicator action in a total volume of 60 ml. With higher concentrations of CPH over-titration occurs.

CPH has many advantages over most of the existing redox indicators in that 1) it is more sensitive requiring less indicator correction, 2) it works in acetic acid medium and (3) the end-point colour is more stable.

Titration of 0.1-0.05N ascorbic acid

The determination of ascorbic acid is of great importance because of its extensive use as vitamin 'c' and reducing titrant. It is oxidized to dehydroascorbic acid by cerium(IV) sulphate with the loss of two electrons as follows :

Ferroin, barium diphenylaminesulphonate (DS), NPA and Rh²⁴ were proposed in the titration of 0.1N ascorbic acid in 0.75-1.50M sulphuric acid solution containing 1 ml of syrupy phosphoric acid. Rh requires day light to give greenish fluorescence which is quenched by slight excess of cerium(IV) sulphate. With ferroin, cerium(IV) sulphate should be added in fractions of a drop with the aid of a thin glass rod near the end-point. DS and NPA give varying results with varying concentrations of indicators. CPH indicator gives sharp colour change from colourless to pink at the equivalence point in 1-2M acetic or 0.5-1.0M sulphuric acid solution containing 2-6 ml of 10M phosphoric acid in a total volume of 60 ml. The end-point colour is stable for about 50 minutes. Precipitation is seen in higher concentration of acetic acid and unstable end-points are obtained in higher concentration of sulphuric acid. CPH gives sharp end-points in hydrochloric acid media ranging from 1.0-2.0M in the presence of 2-3 ml of 10M phosphoric acid. To get stable and bright end-points, 1 ml of CPH should be added near the end-point. Higher concentrations of phosphoric acid give premature end-points and lower concentrations give sluggish end-points. The end-point colour is stable for about 60-40 minutes.

It was found that 0.8-2.0 ml of 0.1% CPH in acetic acid and 1.0-2.5 ml in hydrochloric or sulphuric acid media are necessary for proper indicator action in a total volume of 60 ml. Higher concentration of CPH leads to slightly higher titre values.

Titration of ascorbic acid in phosphoric acid medium

Phosphoric acid has some advantages over sulphuric, hydrochloric or acetic acid as titration medium. It reduces the formal potential of cerium(IV)/cerium(III) system to a value of 1.22V²⁵. The redox potential of ascorbic acid-dehydroascorbic acid is reported to be 185 mV in a solution of pH 7 and -12 mV to +326 mV in a solution of pH range 8.7-1.05²⁶. This redox potential increases to 445-464 mV in 1-2M phosphoric acid²⁴. This increased potential affords protection to the ascorbic acid against atmospheric oxidation. Moreover, phosphoric acid complexes any heavy metal ions present which catalyze the atmospheric oxidation of ascorbic acid. Hence very small amounts of ascorbic acid can be determined in phosphoric acid medium. Ferroin²⁶ functions only in 12-13M phosphoric acid. CPH gives sharp colour change from colourless to pink

at the equivalence point in the titration of ascorbic acid (1.0-170 mg) with 0.002-0.1N cerium(IV) sulphate in 1-2M phosphoric acid solution. Below this range of acid premature end-points are obtained. Above this range overtitration occurs. The end point colour is stable for about 70 min.

It was found that 0.8-2.0 ml of 0.1% CPH is necessary in the titration of ascorbic acid with 0.1-0.05N cerium(IV) sulphate for proper indicator action in a total volume of 60 ml. 0.4-0.7 ml of 0.1% CPH is necessary in the titration with 0.01-0.002N cerium(IV) sulphate for proper indicator action in a total volume of 35 ml.

CPH can be used for the determination of ascorbic acid in the presence of ten-fold excess of oxalic, citric, tartaric, succinic and malic acids, glucose, fructose and sucrose in phosphoric acid medium as these organic compounds do not interfere. It can also be used in sulphuric, hydrochloric or acetic acid media in presence of these organic compounds except oxalic acid.

Comparison with other indicators

CPH has advantages over NPA and DS in that i) it gives sharper end-points and more accurate values, ii) it functions in four acid media while NPA, DS and Rh function only in sulphuric acid medium and iii) it has less indicator correction. It is superior to ferroin because i) it works in 1-2M phosphoric acid medium, ii) it functions in hydrochloric and acetic acid media, iii) it has smaller indicator correction and (iv) it gives sharper end-points.

Determination of ascorbic acid in citrus fruit juices

Ascorbic acid present in citrus fruit juices has been determined by a number of chemical methods²⁷⁻²⁸ in which no internal indicator has been used.

The extraction of juice from citrus fruits like lemons and oranges should be done quickly to prevent aerial oxidation of ascorbic acid before analysis. A known volume of the extracted juice is immediately diluted to 25 ml with phosphoric acid so as to give 3M with respect to phosphoric acid which prevents aerial oxidation. The solution is titrated with 0.005N cerium(IV) sulphate using 1 ml of 0.1% CPH to the appearance of pink colour.

The results of the cerium(IV) sulphate method compare very favourably with those obtained by the indophenol method. The proposed method has the advantages of sharper end-points, increased stability of the reagents, greater simplicity and rapidity and more reproducible results.

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